

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

EDIBLE COATINGS FOR EGGS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to study to edible coatings for eggs. To achieve the scientific goal in this article are used descriptive-analytical method, study of various scientific literature about edible coatings for eggs, systematic approach, comparative analysis, method of observation, induction, deduction, etc.. After researching the scientific works, it was found that there are various edible coatings that preserve the quality and extend the shelf life of eggs. The obtained results may lead to the possibility of using different components and/or combinations of them in the composition of new edible coatings, as well as to conduct research on their influence about quality and duration of storage of eggs.

Keywords: edible coatings, quality, food, eggs.

Introduction

Eggs have been a human food since ancient times. They are one of perfect protein foods and have other high quality nutrients. Eggs are readily digested and can provide a significant portion of the nutrients required daily for growth and maintenance of humans. They are utilized in many ways both in the food industry and the home. Chicken eggs are the most produced [1].

The egg is surrounded by a 0.2–0.4 mm thick calcareous and porous shell. Shells of chicken eggs are white-yellow to brown. The inside of the shell of the egg is with two closely adhering inner and outer membranes. The two membranes of eggs to form an air space, the so-called air cell. The air cell is approx. 5 mm in diameter in fresh eggs and increases in size during storage. This quality parameter can be used to determine the age of eggs. The egg white is an aqueous, faintly straw-tinted, gel-like liquid, consisting of three fractions that differ in viscosity. The inner portion of the egg, the yolk, is surrounded by albumen. The average weight of a chicken egg is 58 g. Its main components are with average values water: (~74%), protein (~12%), and lipids (~11%) [1].

Eggs are perishable and can rapidly lose their quality due to loss of moisture and carbon dioxide through nearly 10,000 tiny pores. The pores in the eggshell facilitate the penetration of certain microorganisms into the interior of eggs and contaminate the internal content [2].

Food industry variety of methods are used for decontaminating the surface of eggs (dry cleaning or washing with water which usually containing a sanitizing agent (e.g., sodium hypochlorite) [2].

Eggshell washing is usually followed by chilled storage. This method could injury the cuticle which may facilitate moisture loss, weight loss and transmission of microorganisms through the shell [2].

Non-thermal processing methods (such as electron beam) is an alternative method of preservation for the whole shell egg quality and safety. However, irradiation under aerobic conditions caused the development of off-flavor and oxidative changes [2].

Considerable attention has been given to the development of edible coatings for preservation of eggs, from polysaccharides, proteins, or lipids, or their combination. Edible coatings prevent moisture losses, weight loss, while selectively allowing for controlled exchange of important gases (oxygen, carbon dioxide and ethylene), which are involved in respiration processes of products. Edible coating can also provide surface sterility and prevent loss of other important components. Generally, its thickness is less than 0.3 mm. Edible coatings prevent the penetration of microorganisms into shell eggs. As a result, they extend their storage time and preserve quality losses. The studies concluded that the coatings helped maintain interior quality, add strength to shell, and reduce microbial load on the shell surface [2,3].

The purpose of this article is to study to edible coatings for eggs.

Methodology

To achieve the scientific goal in this article are used descriptive-analytical method, study of various scientific literature about edible coatings for eggs, systematic approach, comparative analysis, method of observation, induction, deduction, etc..

Results and discussion

Edible coatings can be used to maintain the quality of chicken eggs during storage. In science paper study the quality of chicken eggs during 21 days of storage (at room temperature) coated with *whey protein isolate* and *chitosan edible coating* with the addition of *0.1% sodium tripolyphosphate*. The results shows that eggs coated with edible coating from whey protein isolate and chitosan with the addition of 0.1% sodium tripolyphosphate had a very significant effect on the quality indicators (haugh value of egg units, egg white pH, egg yolk pH, foaming power of eggs, and total contamination of *Salmonella* sp.) The study found that the edible coating can preserve the quality of chicken eggs during storage at room temperature [4].

In the study in Sri Lanka is researched quality of 300 chicken eggs coated the edible oil coatings during storage at room temperature. The eggs were randomly divided into five treatments were: *Sesame oil* coated

eggs (T1), *coconut oil* coated eggs (T2), *olive oil* coated eggs (T3), *mustard oil* coated eggs (T4) and uncoated eggs (T5). The following quality indicators are used in the scientific research: eggs weight loss (%), Haugh Unit (HU), Yolk index (YI), Albumen pH, Yolk pH and Air Cell depth. The results proved that, olive oil coated eggs significantly maintained a lower Weight loss (%), lower albumen pH, lowest yolk pH and maintained a higher Yolk Index (%), highest Haugh Unit during the storage time at 32 °C than followed by T1, T2 and T4. Uncoated eggs show significantly lower quality than coated eggs. The research has shown that that Olive oil edible coating is most suitable to preserve eggs and extending the shelf life of eggs in Sri Lanka [5].

In the article is to investigate the effect of *gum arabic coatings* (1% gum arabic (G1), 5% gum arabic (G5), 10% gum arabic (G10) solution and control) on the quality characteristics of table eggs during of storage (28 days) at 4°C and 25°C. The quality characteristics of the eggs included weight loss, specific gravity, shell strength, Haugh unit, yolk index, and albumen pH. The eggs coated with 10% gum arabic solution had the lowest egg weight loss and albumen pH, and the highest egg specific gravity at the end of storage. In the research no significant differences between gum arabic coated and control eggs for shell strength, Haugh unit or yolk index. Eggs stored at 4°C for 28 days had a lower weight loss and albumen pH and higher egg specific gravity, Haugh unit and yolk index than eggs stored at 25°C. The obtained results suggest that applying a 10% gum arabic coating to eggs preserve their quality for a longer period during storage [6].

In the study of Derelioğlu and Turgay [7], *chitosan-coatings* made with different additives - acetic, lactic, propionic, gallic and caffeic acids and used for coating *chicken* and *quail* eggs to established their effect on the quality and shelf-life of the eggs. Shelf-life study of (weight loss, Haugh unit, yolk index, albumen pH, mineral levels and shell breaking strength) the coating formulations were investigated for 4 weeks. All chitosan coatings coated samples (chicken and quail eggs) showed greater interior (weight loss, Haugh unit, yolk index, albumen pH) and exterior quality (shell breaking strength) than non-coated samples [7].

Goal of the other research is to determine quality of eggs coated with edible films and coatings and their the opportunity to extend shelf-life of eggs under refrigeration storage. Edible films and coatings with different compositions (*paraffin wax*, *mineral oil*, *soy protein isolate*, and *whey protein isolate* (WPI)) were applied to fresh chicken eggs stored for 12 weeks refrigerated storage at 7°C. The quality indicators of eggs with edible films and coatings are: Haugh units, albumen pH, yolk pH, albumen CO₂ content, vitelline membrane strength, water loss, shell strength, and shell color. The results shows that coated eggs maintained higher Haugh units beyond 6 week compared with the uncoated eggs. The eggs coated with edible films and coatings maintained a higher CO₂ content and lower albumen pH than the uncoated eggs during the storage period. Edible films and coatings (oil, wax, WPI) for eggs with extend shelf-life over 6 weeks [8].

In the study is research the quality changes and shelf life of *chitosan* coated eggs during storage measured at different temperature of 5, 20 and 35 °C. The obtained results shows that the quality of eggs, egg yolk coefficient, and Huff units all decreased with the extension of storage time, and the diameter of the air chambers of eggs shows an increasing trend with the extension of storage time. The high temperature (20 and 35 °C) has a significant effect on the quality deterioration than the low temperature (5°C) storage. According to Pearson correlation analysis of each quality index and Huff unit value of eggs (coated and noncoated with edible coatings), yolk coefficient can be used as the most relevant index to predict the shelf life of eggs. According to the variation of egg quality, the dynamic model and Arrhenius equation of yolk coefficient have good fitness [9].

In the study results shows that *casein-chitosan edible coatings* with the addition of TiO₂ 1% solution (5 mL could preserve quality of chicken eggs during storage period (7 - 14 days). The quality of the eggs is survey by the following quality indicators: the yolk-albumen index, Haugh Unit, albumen pH value, and yolk colour. In the tests done on the samples, it was found that the storage period of 7 days showed a better result [10].

Figure 1. Internal eggs condition storage for 7 and 14 days [10].

Effects of the different edible coatings (*whey protein isolate*, *chitosan* and *shellac*) on quality of fresh eggs (the interior quality and sensory evaluation) are evaluated based on during of storage for 4 weeks. The research shows that all egg weights and albumen heights decreased and albumen pH increased. The lowest results about weight loss was observed in shellac-coated eggs - 0.75%. Eggs coated with chitosan and whey protein edible coatings with also had significantly lower weight loss than uncoated eggs. The albumen pH of the non-coated eggs was significantly higher than that of eggs with applied edible coatings and increased during storage time. The Haugh unit and yolk-index values of all coated eggs were significantly higher than those of non-coated. Eggs coated with the shellac coatings had the highest value of Haugh unit and yolk index. Chitosan and shellac coatings are effectively maintained grade "A" eggs for at least 2 weeks more than control and 1 week more than whey protein isolate coatings. The sensory evaluation shows that, shellac coatings has highest glossiness, but lowest general acceptability. Eggs with applied whey protein coatings had significantly higher general acceptability. The study

shows that various edible coatings improved the shelf life of eggs during storage [11].

In the article is to researched of the effectiveness of *rice protein coatings with propolis* (5 or 10%) on retain of quality (weight loss, Haugh unit (HU), albumen pH, yolk index (YI), shell strength, and scanning electron microscopy in uncoated eggs (control treatment)) of fresh eggs during storage at 20°C for 6 weeks. The Haugh unit (HU) and yolk index (YI) were higher in coated eggs. Non-coated eggs showed the highest weight loss (5.39%), compared to eggs coated with rice protein coatings (4.27%) and rice protein coatings with propolis at 5% (4.11%) and 10% (4.40%). Non-coated eggs had the worst Haugh unit (HU) (58.47), albumen pH (9.48), and YI (0.33) after 6 weeks of storage. The results about scanning electron microscopy demonstrated a lower surface porosity in coated eggshell. It is indicating that the use of the coating may provide a protective barrier properties against the transfer of gases and moisture. In conclusion rice protein coatings with propolis helped to preserve egg quality for a longer time compared to non-coated eggs [12].

Figure 2. Scanning electron microscopy ($\times 250$) of uncoated eggshell (picture A) and coated eggs (pictures B to D) after 6 wk of storage. RPC: rice protein concentrate coating [12].

In the study is to evaluate the eggs quality coated *cassava and yam starches coatings* during stored at 25 and 5 °C for 28 days. The treatments with edible coatings used were the following: fresh eggs (T1), without coating stored at 5 °C (T2) and 25 °C (T3), with cassava (T4) and yam (T5), starches coatings. The eggs were examined according to the following quality indicators: egg weight; weight loss; albumen, yolk and shell percentages; Haugh Units (HU); yolk color; and yolk and albumen pH. The eggs during storage at a refrigerated temperature showed better values for Haugh Units. The eggs stored with a of cassava and yam starch coatings had a reduction of internal quality for Haugh Units. The

parameters albumen, pH of the coating of yam starch had good results about the quality of the eggs during storage for 28 days at room temperature (25 °C) [13].

In the study, eggs are coated with edible coatings prepared from *sweet potato starch* and varying levels of *thyme essential oil*, including 0 (control), 2%, 4%, and 6%. The quality and safety of the coated and uncoated eggs during five weeks of storage at 25°C have been studied. The application of 4% edible coatings maintained the quality and safety of eggs two weeks longer than uncoated eggs. This study showed that the edible coatings could be useful in extending the shelf life and delaying changes of quality (Haugh units, yolk

index, shell breaking strength, shell color, albumen pH, and weight loss) of eggs during storage time [14].

Effects of *chitosan*, *whey protein concentrate*, *mineral oil* and/or *soybean oil coatings* on egg quality (Haugh unit, yolk index, weight loss, albumen pH and emulsifying capacity) were compared at 25 and 4°C, respectively, during 5 and 20 weeks of storage. Shelf life is extend 4 weeks by mineral oil and soybean oil and 2 weeks by chitosan and whey protein concentrate coatings longer than that observed for noncoated eggs at 25°C. Eggs coated with mineral oil and soybean oil maintained AA grade for 20 weeks at 4 °C. Weight loss of soybean oil coated eggs was <1% after 5 weeks at 25°C and after 20 weeks at 4°C. Yolk index and emulsifying capacity were more correlated at 25°C than at 4°C. Mineral oil and soybean oil are more effective coating materials, with soybean oil providing a more cost-effective coating for extending shelf life of eggs [15].

In a study to evaluate the effect of thermal treatments using different water temperatures and immersion times, as well as the application of eggshell coatings using edible materials on eggshell quality after storage for 4 weeks at room temperature (22.8 ± 4.4 °C). The eggs are treatments consisted of a control group without any treatment (T1), three groups treated thermally: 56 °C/32 minutes (T2); 56 °C/20 minutes (T3); 56 °C/10 minutes (T4); and *two groups with gelatin 2% (T5) and 5% NaCl solution (T6)*. After storage, it was found that the heat treatments at 56 °C for 10, 20 and 32 minutes provided maintenance of the albumen height, which reflected the values of the Haugh units but negatively influenced the albumen foam stability. The treatment of eggs with 5% NaCl solution showed the lowest lipid oxidation rate and the best albumen foam stability. The proposed treatments (thermal or coatings) of eggs, individually, caused significant improvements on some eggs quality evaluated after 30 days of during storage [16].

A *pectin-based coatings* effectively preserve quality of eggs during of storage 5 week (35 days). Based the results about on weight loss and Haugh unit values, the pectin coating increased the shelf life of eggs at ambient temperature compared with that of uncoated eggs. Future studies are needed to investigate whether the use of pectin also contributes to the microbiological quality of eggshells [17].

In the article is to studied effect of edible coatings on the quality of table eggs during storage to different temperature (4°C & 30°C). The data showed that eggs stored at high temperatures (30°C) lost weight more quickly than the eggs kept at (4°C). Every sample under examination reduction in yolk index and Haugh value over the course of during storage. The rate of reduction is much higher in samples during stored at high temperature (30°C). The data shows that as storage time extended, the pH values for the tested for coated with *aloe vera gel* and uncoated eggs rose. Egg albumen's ability to froth and the stability of its froth are both negatively impacted by the rise in pH values that arises from storage duration and temperature of storage. All eggs experienced increase in the total bacterial count along with the progressing of the storage period. The increment

was much higher for the eggs stored at high temperature (30°C) [18].

After researching the scientific literature, it was found that there is a wide variety of different edible coatings (*whey protein isolate* and *chitosan edible coating* with the addition of *0.1% sodium tripolyphosphate*; *sesame oil coating*, *coconut oil coating*, *olive oil coatings*, *mustard oil coating*; *gum arabic coatings*; *chitosan-coatings*; coatings from *paraffin wax*, *mineral oil*, *soy protein isolate*, and *whey protein isolate (WPI)*; *casein-chitosan coatings* with the addition of *TiO₂*; edible coatings from *whey protein isolate*, *chitosan* and *shellac*; *rice protein coatings with propolis*; *cassava and yam starches coatings*; *sweet potato starch coatings* and varying levels of *thyme essential oil*; coatings from *chitosan*, *whey protein concentrate*, *mineral oil* and/or *soybean oil coatings*; *gelatin coatings*; *pectin-based coatings* and *aloe vera coatings*). The various edible coatings presented preserve the quality and extend the during storage of eggs.

Conclusion

After researching the scientific works, it was found that there are various edible coatings composed of polysaccharides, lipids and proteins or a mixture of these that preserve the quality and extend the shelf life of eggs. The obtained results may lead to the possibility of using different components and/or combinations of them in the composition of new edible coatings, as well as to conduct research on their influence about quality and duration of storage of eggs.

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